

OPTIMUM DESIGN OF FILAMENT WOUND MULTIZONAL COMPOSITE SHELLS

E.V. Morozov

Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Natal, Durban 4041, South Africa

SUMMARY: The present paper deals with the development of a dedicated optimum design procedure for the multizonal filament wound composite shells of minimum mass. The composite shells of revolution with the specified geometrical shape are considered. It is assumed that the filament wound shell consists of a number of helical layers of various lengths. The set of design parameters includes the total number of layers, coefficients of reinforcement density for each layer, reinforcement orientation angles, and locations of the starting points for helical winding. The design technique is based on the sequential optimising algorithm specifically developed for the problem discussed. Manufacturing constraints are taken into account and the synthesis of laminated composite shell is performed. The numerical results obtained for symmetrically loaded composite shell demonstrate the possibility of a significant mass reduction.

KEYWORDS: optimum design, filament winding, reinforcement orientation, multizonal composite shells, optimum control theory.

INTRODUCTION

The filament wound composite shells of revolution with specified geometrical shape and loaded by distributed internal pressure are considered in the present paper. For this type of problem the applied loads are not necessarily carried entirely by fibres but matrix has to serve as a partial load bearing constituent. Correspondingly, more sophisticated mechanical models of composite materials should be implemented to take into consideration the strength and stiffness of the matrix material. Besides, the manufacturing constraints must be imposed in order to take into account the main features of the helical filament winding. The multizonal thin-walled shells are fabricated by helical filament winding of successive elementary helical twin layers of various lengths as shown in Fig. 1. The set of design parameters describing a particular laminated composite structure includes the fibre orientation, thickness distribution, stacking sequences, and number of layers. Additionally, the locations of the starting points for helical winding are included into the set of design parameters and the length of each helical layer should be determined at the design stage. The design methodology discussed in this work let us possibility to avoid the utilisation of computationally expensive general optimisation algorithms and universal methods. The basic design concept applied to the optimisation procedure is closely adjusted to the specific structural design problem.

Fig. 1: Multizonal composite shell of revolution

It provides the opportunity to consider all of the important structural features of the particular composite structure and related manufacturing technology. From this close consideration of the real structure and fabrication process we can obtain some specific features and hints that allow us to find effective short cuts and obtain the optimum solution. The formulation of the optimum design problem is presented first. The optimisation procedure is then introduced and numerical results discussed.

FORMULATION OF DESIGN PROBLEM

Multizonal filament wound composite shells consist of a system of layers of various lengths (see Fig.1). This type of composite shells is fabricated by the filament winding of successive elementary helical twin layers. The twin elementary layer consists of two unidirectional reinforced plies symmetrically oriented at angles of $+\phi$ and $-\phi$. In case of n -layered shell we have n unknown continuous functions $\phi_i(y)$ (reinforcement trajectories), $i=1, \dots, n$, where n is the total number of twin layers. If all of n twin layers have the same length we have a conventional type of filament wound composite shell. For such a shell filament winding of each twin layer starts at the same initial location of the shell cross section $y = y_1^{(1)}$. It has been proved that the mass of composite shell loaded by the distributed internal pressure might be significantly reduced as a result of the implementation of a multizonal filament winding [1].

The multizonal shell can be fabricated if the helical filament winding of twin layers starts at the various cross sections located at the points $y_1^{(1)}, y_1^{(2)}, y_1^{(3)}, \dots, y_1^{(n)}$ (see Fig.1). These parameters represent another group of design variables to be determined during the optimisation procedure.

The minimum mass (or volume) of the shell

$$V = \sum_{i=1}^n V_i \quad (1)$$

has been chosen as a quality criterion. In this equation V_i denotes the volume of the $\pm\phi_i$ twin elementary layer. Volume of the i th layer can be expressed in the following functional form

$$V_i = 2\pi \int_{y_1^{(i)}}^{y_a^{(i)}} r(y) \sqrt{1 + (r')^2} h_i(y) dy \quad (2)$$

where $y_1^{(i)}$ is the co-ordinate of the starting point of filament winding; $y_a^{(i)}$ is the co-ordinate of the butt-end of the shell as shown in Fig. 1; $r(y)$ is the radius of the cross-section of the shell as a function of y co-ordinate ; $r' = dr / dy$, and $h_i(y)$ is the thickness distribution function of the elementary twin layer. The thickness of a filament wound layer can be calculated as follows

$$h_i(y) = \frac{S_i}{2\pi r(y) \cos \phi_i} \quad (3)$$

where S_i = (the coefficient of reinforcement density of elementary twin layer). This parameter can be calculated as $S_i = \omega b \delta$, where ω is the number of filaments (or tapes) passing through the cross-section of the shell; b is the width of the tape being wound; δ - is the thickness of the elementary unidirectional reinforced ply.

In order to provide an uninterrupted process of helical winding the parameter S_i should stay constant for any cross section in the interval $y_1^{(i)} \leq y \leq y_a^{(i)}$. Thus, in order to solve the problem we need to find the values of the design unknown variables S_i instead of the unknown functions $h_i(y)$. Such a substitution significantly simplifies the solution of the optimum design problem.

Another manufacturing constraint must be imposed onto the reinforcement trajectories $\phi_i(y)$. Namely, the conditions of fibres equilibrium on the mandrel surface should be satisfied. These requirements can be expressed analytically in the following form [2]

$$(\sin \phi_i)' = \frac{\lambda_i \beta}{r} \sin^2 \phi_i \left(1 + \frac{rr''}{1+(r')^2} \right) - \frac{r'}{r} \sin \phi_i - \frac{\lambda_i \beta r''}{1+(r')^2}, \quad |\lambda_i(y)| \leq 1 \quad (4)$$

where β is a friction coefficient, primes denote the first derivative of a function with respect to the y coordinate, and $\lambda_i(y)$ are the unknown functions of control. Upon integrating this equation, we can obtain various trajectories $\phi_i(y)$ for specified functions $\lambda_i(y)$. In particular case, for $\lambda_i \equiv 0$, the equation (4) represents geodetical trajectories. If $\lambda_i(y) \equiv \pm 1$ we have the lines of maximum deviation from the corresponding geodetical trajectory of reinforcement orientation.

During the filament winding process the fibres or tapes make U-turns at the initial points of each helical twin layer. This means that filaments should be tangent to the circumference $r = r_1^{(i)}(y_1^{(i)})$ and correspondingly $\phi_1^{(i)} = \phi_i(y_1^{(i)}) = \pi/2$. This condition should be satisfied for $i = 2, 3, \dots, n$. For the first layer it is possible to have an arbitrary value of angle $\phi_1^{(1)}$ by starting the winding process at the position different from $y = y_1$ ($y < y_1$).

The form of strength constraints to be imposed on the design variables depends on the failure criteria. The geometry of the considered composite shell is prescribed and different from the shape of isotensoid. This means that the matrix material carries a significant portion of the external load. To satisfy these conditions the following strength criteria can be used [1], [3]

$$|\sigma_1^{(i)}(\phi_i)| \leq \bar{\sigma}_1, \quad \bar{\sigma}_2^- \leq \sigma_2^{(i)}(\phi_i) \leq \bar{\sigma}_2^+, \quad |\tau_{12}^{(i)}(\phi_i)| \leq \bar{\tau}_{12}, \quad (i = 1, \dots, n) \quad (5)$$

where $\sigma_1^{(i)}(\phi_i)$, $\sigma_2^{(i)}(\phi_i)$ are the stresses acting along the fibres and in the orthogonal direction of the elementary layer respectively, $\tau_{12}^{(i)}(\phi_i)$ is the shear stress, and $\bar{\sigma}_1$, $\bar{\sigma}_2^+$, $\bar{\sigma}_2^-$, $\bar{\tau}_{12}$ are the ultimate stresses for unidirectionally reinforced composite material. Signs “+” and “-” correspond to the tensile and compressive strength. The stresses can be calculated for the specified mechanical properties of composite material, shell geometry, and external load using the approach presented in [1], [3].

In terms of the considered above conditions, requirements, and notations the optimisation problem can be formulated as follows

$$V = \sum_{i=1}^n V_i \rightarrow \min, \quad V_i = S_i \int_{y_1^{(i)}}^{y_a} \frac{\sqrt{1+(r')^2}}{\cos \phi_i(y)} dy \quad (6)$$

$$(\sin \phi_i)' = \frac{\lambda_i(y)\beta}{r} \sin^2 \phi_i \left(1 + \frac{rr''}{1+(r')^2} \right) - \frac{r'}{r} \sin \phi_i - \frac{\lambda_i(y)\beta r''}{1+(r')^2} \quad (7)$$

$$\phi_1^{(i)} = \phi_i(y_1^{(i)}) = \pi/2 \quad (8)$$

$$|\lambda_i(y)| \leq 1 \quad (9)$$

$$|\sigma_1^{(i)}(\phi_i)| \leq \bar{\sigma}_1, \quad \bar{\sigma}_2^- \leq \sigma_2^{(i)}(\phi_i) \leq \bar{\sigma}_2^+, \quad |\tau_{12}^{(i)}(\phi_i)| \leq \bar{\tau}_{12}, \quad (i = 1, \dots, n) \quad (10)$$

The equations (7) provide the conditions for equilibrium of filaments on the mandrel surface during the helical winding process. Equalities (8) provide the conditions for uninterrupted filament winding which requires the fibres to make a U-turn at the initial point of each helical layer.

In order to solve this problem we have to find the trajectories of reinforcement orientation $\phi_i(y)$, control functions $\lambda_i(y)$, the values of parameter S_i , and the number of layers n . The optimal set of these design variables (functions and parameters) should provide the minimum of the objective functional (6).

OPTIMISATION PROCEDURE

For the specified trajectories of reinforcement the pilot design project of multizonal shell can be obtained on the basis of the design procedure presented in [1], [3]. Consider the layer with number i . From the conditions (7) and (8) we can see that all feasible trajectories of reinforcement will be located in the area restricted by the maximum deviation lines with $\lambda_i = +1$ and $\lambda_i = -1$ as shown in Fig.2. These lines could be found from equation (7) for the specified control functions $\lambda_i(y)$. Assume that the trajectories for the remaining layers with numbers $i+1, \dots, n$ are known. Let us define the length of the i -th layer as the length of the segment $c_i = y_a - y_1^{(i)}$. If we increase the values of control function $\lambda_i(y)$ from -1 to 1 for

the i -th layer, then the lengths of the remaining layers c_{i+1}, \dots, c_n will decrease. This reduction in length occurs due to the fact that as the λ_i is increased the fibre orientation angle will increase correspondingly causing the strength constraints to become active in a shorter distance measured along the y direction. Additionally the increase of angles $\phi_i(y)$ causes the decrease in the values of parameter S_i . Internal pressure loading typically generates large hoop stresses. As the fibre orientation angle approaches the circumferential orientation, a smaller values of the reinforcement density would be required. New co-ordinates of the initial points $y_1^{(i+1)}, \dots, y_1^{(n)}$ are determined by the method presented in [3]. The values of angles $\phi_a^{(i+1)}, \dots, \phi_a^{(n)}$ will also increase in this process (see Fig.2).

Fig.2 Feasible reinforcement trajectories for the i -th and $(i+1)$ -th helical layers

Correspondingly the total volume value of the shell will decrease as a result of the reduction in the integration interval length, values of the S_i parameters, and the values of $\cos \phi_a^{(i)}$ (see equation (6)). Thus, if the trajectories of all the layers, begin with the $(i+1)$ th layer, are known we should assign $\lambda_i(y) \equiv 1$ for the layer with the number i to decrease the total volume of the shell. According to this analysis the optimum shell should consist of layers with trajectories of reinforcement that have initial angles $\phi_i(y_1^{(i)}) = \pi / 2$ and $\lambda_i \equiv +1$, $i = 1, \dots, n$. The co-ordinates of initial points for each layer and the total number of zones (layers) n are determined using the design procedure presented in [3]. This solution for the shell design could be considered as the close approximation of the so-called fully stressed structure. At the same time, due to the composite nature of the material considered here there is possibility to improve this solution. We will consider the result obtained above as a pilot design of the composite shell. It has been shown in [2], that the optimum reinforcement trajectory for a twin helical layer consists of two maximum deviation lines separated by the only one control-shift point $y^{(i)} = \tilde{y}^{(i)}$. The control function takes the value $\lambda_i = -1$ for $y_1^{(i)} \leq y \leq \tilde{y}^{(i)}$ and $\lambda_i = +1$ for the interval $\tilde{y}^{(i)} \leq y \leq y_a$. This solution was obtained in absence of the strength constraints imposed onto the design parameters. This fact allows us to provide the further mass reduction of the shell. We can consider the function $V_i(\tilde{y}^{(i)})$ in the interval $y_1^{(i)} \leq \tilde{y}^{(i)} \leq y_a$ as shown in Fig. 3 for each layer starting with $i = n$. For the last layer ($i = n$) the optimum location of the control-shift point $\tilde{y}^{(n)}$ can be found from the direct minimisation of the volume V_n . This procedure can be organised as a numerical process in

which the possible candidates for the optimum control-shift point are considered sequentially within the feasible interval $y_1^{(n)} \leq y \leq y_a$ according to [1]. At every step of this process the strength constraints should be satisfied and the total volume of the shell calculated. Then the next layer with number $i = n - 1$ should be considered and the described above process must be repeated. In this case, the construction of the curves $V_n(\tilde{y})$ and $V_{n-1}(\tilde{y})$ is performed for each point from the segment $y_1^{(n-1)} \leq y \leq y_a$. The new values of V_{n-1} and V_n are added to the volume of the previous $n - 2$ layers and compared with the previous total value of the volume. As a result we obtain a new design solution for the shell which consists of $n - 2$ layers with $\lambda_i(y) \equiv +1$. The last two layers of the shell have combined reinforcement trajectories. The process is repeated until the total volume of the shell is decreased and the strength constraints are satisfied.

Fig. 3 Volume V_i of the i -th layer as a function of co-ordinate $\tilde{y}^{(i)}$.

According to the described above improvement procedure the total volume of the shell should decrease but at the same time the values of the angles $\phi_i(y)$, $i = n, n - 1, n - 2, \dots$ are decreased too causing, on the other hand, the increase in volume value. This increase in volume is much faster than the decrease caused by the improvement procedure. The fast increase in volume is due to the fast change of the limit parameter S_i from $S_i(\lambda_i = -1)$ to $S_i(\lambda_i = +1)$ in comparison with the change of the manufacturing parameter $S = S_M^{(i)}$ from $S_M^{(i)}(\lambda_i = -1)$ to $S_M^{(i)}(\lambda_i = +1)$. For a given thickness δ of elementary filament or tape we can determine the thickness of the twin helical layer $h_a = 2\delta$ at $y = y_a$ (See Fig. 1). Since the thickness h_a is known, the value of parameter $S = S_M^{(i)}$ can be calculated as follows [1]

$$S_M^{(i)} = 2\pi r_a h_a \cos \phi_a^{(i)} \quad (11)$$

As a result the sequential procedure of the design improvement is accomplished fast. The first k layers of the final design are identical to the first k layers of the pilot design. The remaining $n - k$ layers have the combined reinforcement trajectories, consisting of the lines of maximum deviation as indicated above.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

The method has been implemented to the design of the multilayered composite shell of revolution made of the carbon fibre reinforced composite material. Mechanical properties of the unidirectional composite laminae were as follows: $E_1 = 160$ GPa (elasticity modulus along fibres), $E_2 = 19$ GPa (elasticity modulus across fibres), $G_{12} = 9$ GPa (shear modulus, $\bar{\sigma}_1 = 320$ MPa, $\bar{\sigma}_2^+ = 7$ MPa, $\bar{\sigma}_2^- = 50$ MPa, $\bar{\tau}_{12} = 30$ MPa. The thickness of the elementary ply δ is equal to 0.25 mm.

The total mass of the shell wound at angles $\pm\phi_i$ to the meridian along the geodetic lines ($\lambda_i = 0$, $i = 1, \dots, n$) was equal to 13.75 kg. The shell consisted of 8 twin elementary layers. The optimum design obtained on the basis of the described above approach represented the multizonal shell with the mass of 10.99 kg. The design process has been converged when the number of layers was equal to 6. At the same time the set of associated initial co-ordinates $y_1^{(2)}, y_1^{(3)}, \dots, y_1^{(6)}$ has been found. The first three layers were reinforced with the filament winding along the lines of maximum deviation with $\lambda_i \equiv 1$, ($i = 1, 2, 3$). The 4th, 5th, and 6th layers of the shell had the combined trajectories of reinforcement. Each combined trajectory had the only one control-shift point from $\lambda_i = -1$ to $\lambda_i = +1$. The total 20% mass reduction in comparison with the multilayered shell with the geodetic trajectories of reinforcement has been obtained.

CONCLUSIONS

Optimum design problem has been formulated for multizonal filament wound composite shell of revolution. The dedicated design procedure has been developed to create the structure of minimum mass. Manufacturing constraints have been taken into account and the synthesis of multilayered shell has been performed. The numerical results obtained for filament wound carbon-reinforced composite shell demonstrate the possibility of significant mass reduction (up to 20%) in comparison with the design based on the conventional filament winding performed along the geodetic trajectories of the reinforcement orientation.

REFERENCES

1. Morozov, E.V., "Optimum Design of Filament Wound Composite Shells", *Optimal Structural Design*, Chapter 8, Edited by V.V.Vasiliev and Z. Gurdal. Technomic Publ. Co., Inc., Lancaster, PA 17604, 1998.
2. Morozov, E.V., "Optimal Reinforcement Trajectories for a Composite Shell of Revolution Formed by the Winding Method", *Mechanics of Composite Materials*, 1985, Vol. 21, No.2, pp.227-231.
3. Morozov, E.V., "Structural optimization of multilayered and multizonal composite shells", *Proceedings of the International Conference "Mechanics in Design" (MID'98)*, Nottingham, 6-9 July 1998, Chandos Publ. (Oxford) Ltd., 1998, pp.356 – 364.